

OPTIMAL DESIGN OF PV-WIND-GRID SYSTEM FOR A VILLAGE IN INDIA USING HOMER

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Abstract:

The goal of this paper is to identify the optimal hybrid technology combination for generating electricity from a mix of renewable energy sources in order to meet the electrical load requirement of Bohar village, Haryana, India (28.52°N, 76.42°E). The village's geographical data was taken into account while determining the renewable energy sources. Additionally, various size and type combinations of renewable energy resources were explored, and the optimal component size was determined using the HOMER modeling programme, taking into account the Net present cost (NPC) and cost of energy (COE).

Key Words: PV, Wind, HOMER, Hybrid System, NPC, COE.

Introduction:

The global usage of renewable energy in various applications is increasing because of degradation of natural resources and the environmental concerns. The latest report of international energy agency report, Global capacity for renewable energy was 2 799 GW by the end of 2020. With a capacity of 1211 GW, hydropower accounted for the world's largest share. The remaining shares of wind and solar energy were equal, with capacity respectively of 733 GW and 714 GW. Global cumulative renewable energy capacity is presented in figure 1.

Figure 1: Globally renewable sources capacity

Renewable is also increasing in India and development of renewable in the nation's overall energy combination increasing very rapidly. India is the 3rd biggest consumer of electricity in the world, with 38 percent (136 GW out of 373 GW) of total renewable-powered energy installed in 2020. In 2016, India pledged to generating 40 percent of all its energy from non-fossil sources by 2030, under the Paris Agreement's and set a goal of 57 percent of its total electricity produced by non-fossil sources by 2027.

On a comparatively bigger scale, standalone solar photovoltaic, wind turbines, bio-diesel were endorsed around the world. These autonomous structures cannot, because they are seasonal, provide a regular source of power supply. For instance, stand-alone solar system during non-sunny days cannot provide reliable power. Owing to substantial variations in the value of wind speeds in every hour during the day and year, the only wind energy system can't fulfill regular demand of load. Likewise, due to low-commercialization of bio-diesel generator fuel, regular supply of bio-diesel petroleum is problematic. Each of these systems, therefore, power generation systems would be essential to satisfy the energy demands [1]. The device used to store energy is typically expensive, and its scale must be reduced to make cost-effective renewable energy system. Garg et al presented a review on the need of the development of microgrids and suggested that hybrid system could overcome the increasing demand of the electricity [2].

The hybrid system consists of one energy source or more than one energy source to build the power supply systems. Photovoltaic is the key energy source in hybrid system and a number of other energy sources can be combined as secondary energy systems, including bio-diesel system, wind energy system and biomass system. There are many different hybrid options, which are preferred according to demand and availability. They are photovoltaic with bio-diesel system, photovoltaic including wind energy system and photovoltaic with bio-gas energy system. The establishment of photovoltaic solar systems in India is based on 20 hectares of land

per MW. Solar energy in India is rapidly growing, almost 7.8% from 2015 to 2019. The 1.6 million MW solar plants can be fitted in India with a surface area of 1 percent. There are large areas of soil adapted to solar energy in all regions of India, more than 8 per cent of its entire unproductive and plant less area. Power plants can produce 2,400 billion kWh (kWh) of 32,000 kilometres of wasteland, double the active industries and the high productivity of irrigated agriculture [3,4]. In the northern region solar power is growing higher and almost 8.4 percent was observed between 2015 and 2019.

The combination of PV and wind sources to make a renewable energy system installed to generate power for the desired load for a selected location blessed with wind and solar velocity. In this system, either PV or wind is required to use as initial energy source which are dependent upon the span of availability of wind/solar energy in the location. A number of other renewable sources such as bio-diesel, diesel-biomass, diesel can also be merged as a secondary source of energy. In the renewable sources, the performance of the both solar and wind systems depends largely on natural cycles and topology of the chosen location [5]. Hence, it can be used only when wind speed and solar installation are sufficient to generate power. In hybrid systems, batteries are charged during times of abundance power age and are released at whatever point there an insufficiency in power is created concerning the nearby interest.

Nayar developed hybrid energy systems to power remote areas of Australia [6]. Numerous configurations have been investigated, including switched, parallel, and series connections. A wind power hybrid system with backup fuel cells has been used [7]. It was discovered that fuel cells are well suited for inaccessible applications when used to meet excess electricity demand. PEM fuel cells can be used to manage the electricity supply in inclement weather and to respond to high load switching. The efficiency of hydrogen conversion to electricity is found to be 42%. Karki et al. used a Monte Carlo simulation method to assist model planners in determining the optimal location, operating policies, and sizing of renewable energy in small isolated communities [8]. A case study on Dahrán has been conducted by Shaadid and Elhadidy to satisfy its power requirement of 620,000 KWh per year by means of a hybrid model, in combination of 175 KW DG and 80KW SPV [9]. The COE of the model has resulted in 0.149 \$ per KWh. Various scenarios have been examined for complications arising in it like excess electricity, emission decrease, unmet load situations and higher energy cost. Chauhan & Saini has examined standalone technology-based system like biomass, biogas, solar, hydro etc. and gathered systems for off-grid rural electrification in Uttarakhand, India. The barriers and problems are addressed through suitable answers recommended [10]. PV-diesel hybrid models are investigated by Schmitt et al in several ranges from 10 to 30 KW. The results of this study are implemented, about 90% villages of emerging countries might be electrified [11].

The purpose of this article is to discuss the optimal size of various components of hybrid system and to conduct a techno-economic analysis. To do this, the scientists used the HOMER (Hybrid Optimization Model for Electric Renewable) software programme. The paper is organized as follows: Section II contains information on the geographical location, load, available resources, and modeling of system components. The findings are presented and discussed in Section III, and the research is concluded in Section IV.

System Description:

For the optimal configuration and evaluation of the techno-economic viability of HRES based systems, HOMER software developed by NREL (National Renewable Energy Laboratory) is used. The collected data is entered and the optimum configuration found in the HOMER Simulation Tool. The village of Bohar is considered for this research work. It is located in the Rohtak tehsil of the Rohtak district in Haryana, India. The village is comprised of 1617 hectares in total geographical area. Bohar has more than 20,000 inhabitants. In Kanipla village there are approximately 3287 houses.

a). Load Assessment:

The village load requirement is carefully estimated in this research work using existing load profile data. The load was calculated separately for the two distinct seasons that prevail in this region, namely summer (April to October) and winter (November to March) (November to March). Summer season carries a greater load than winter season. The estimated demand for both seasons is meticulously calculated and described in Table 1. Demand estimation is a critical component of the hybrid system design, and it can be enhanced further by incorporating villagers' social information and preferences. The village's total load is classified into two categories.

- Load A: This category contains the load on household appliances. Summer main load is estimated to be 11708.3 kWh/day. The village's residential usage is 3.56 kWh/day. The village's domestic load is 5650.35 kWh/day during the winter season, while home usage is 1.72 kWh/day. The summer season has more primary load as compared to winter season. Figure 2 and 3 represents the 12 month and daily load profile of the load A, respectively.
- Load II: This especially marked of shoppes, street lights, temples, grain mills, water pumping stations, basic health centers, and schools. Summer average load is 221.53 kWh/day, whereas winter average load is 190.04 kWh/day. The secondary load in winter is little bit more compared to summer. Figure 4 and 5 represents the 12 month and daily load profile of the load B, respectively.

Figure 2: Load profile of Bohar village of 12 months of load A

Figure 3: Daily Load profile of Bohar village of load A

Figure 4: Load profile of Bohar village of 12 months of load B

Table 1: Electrical load of Bohar Village

S.No	Load	No. in Use	Power (Watts)	Summers (April-October)		Winters (November-March)		
				Hrs/Day	Wh/Day	Hrs/Day	Wh/Day	
Domestic Appliance Load								
1	LEDs	2	15	6	180	7	210	
2	LEDs	2	12	6	144	7	168	
3	LEDs	2	9	6	108	7	126	
4	Celling fans	2	50	10	1000	0	0	
4	TVs	1	60	3	180	4	240	
5	HVAC System	1	150	8	1200	4	600	
6	Water Pumps*	1*0.30	500	1	150	0.5	75	
7	Refrigerators **	1*0.25	200	12	600	6	300	
8	Total				3562		1719	
A	Primary Load (No. of house (3287))			11708294		5650353		
Commercial Purpose, Temples and Street Light Load								
1	Shops	20	200	10	40000	7	28000	
2	Temples	5	100	3	1500	3	1500	
3	Street lights	100	50	7	35000	9	45000	
4	Flour mills	5	2000	8	80000	8	80000	
5	Water supply pumps	3	3730	3	33570	2	22380	
B1	Total			190070		176880		
Schools and Primary Health Center Load								
1	School	LEDs	80	12	10	9600	10	9600
		Celling fans	40	50	8	16000	0	0

2	Health Centre	LEDs	5	12	6	360	6	360
		Celling fans	5	50	6	1500	0	0
		Refrigerators	1	200	20	4000	16	3200
B2	Total		31460				13160	
Secondary Load : B=B1+B2			221530				190040	

*30% of the total households have a water pump

**25% of total households have refrigerator.

Figure 5: Daily Load profile of Bohar village of load B

b). Resources Assessment:

In this study's simulation, solar, wind, and the grid are all used. The resources are carefully selected in accordance with the geographic conditions of the chosen location.

Solar Radiation:

NASA's (National Aeronautics and Space Administration) surface meteorology and solar energy database is used to obtain the solar radiation data for the selected location as shown in Fig. 6. At the selected location, the annual average solar radiation is 5.29 kWh/m²/day, ranging from 3.5 kWh/m²/day to 6.8 kWh/m²/day, with a clearness index of 0.59. Solar radiation is available almost throughout the year, with the peak occurring in May and the trough occurring in December. Based on the amount of solar radiation available, the PV system's output is calculated to be as follows:

$$E_{PV} = \text{Area} \times \text{Eff.} \times \text{Rad.} \times \text{PPR} \quad (1)$$

E_{PV} = Solar output energy

Area = Solar panel area

Eff. = Panel efficiency (%)

Rad. = yearly solar radiation

PPR = Panel performance ratio

Figure 6: Average irradiation and clearness index

Wind Resource:

The average data of wind speed for last thirty years of the current location is also obtained from NASA as shown in Fig. 7. The minimum wind speed (3.43 m/s) in October. It is observed maximum 5.34 m/s in May with average wind speed of 4.53 m/s. The amount of power that the wind is capable of delivering is described as:

$$P_{WE} = \frac{1}{2} \times \rho \times A \times V_s \times CP(\lambda, \beta) \times \eta_t \times \eta_g \quad (2)$$

ρ = Density of Air

CP = Turbine Performance co-efficient

λ = Ratio of Tip and speed

β = Pitch angle of Blade

V_s = Velocity of Wind

η_t = Wind turbine Efficiency

η_g = Generator Efficiency

A = Blades Area swept

Figure 7: Profile of wind speed profile

Temperature Resources:

The monthly average temperature data for last thirty years for current location is also gathered from NASA as shown in Fig. 8. The minimum temperature is 13.79 °C in the month of the January. It is observed maximum 36.11 °C in June with average wind speed of 25.79 °C.

Figure 8: Monthly average temperatures at the selected location

c). System Simulation:

Because of the intermittent nature of the Renewable energy systems, this power does not have the reliability that would allow it to be utilized. Backup facilities are therefore needed. Batteries are used to provide a redundant backup. The system will only charge the batteries if demand is lower than supply, otherwise the batteries will be in discharging mode. Each configuration is simulated, one by one, to find the most suitable design that fulfils load and system constraints. The system is analyzed in three configurations; PV/wind/grid with on net metering (PVWG-OnNM), PV/wind/grid with off net metering (PVWG-OffNM) and PV/wind (PVW). The systematic designed system in HOMER is represented in Fig. 9.

Figure 9: Designed system in HOMER

PV Modules:

The main source of supplying the household's electric demand is via PV modules. When the PV module's total capacity is selected, it is based on the demand that is not currently being met. Generic flat plate PV is used in this research work. The upper limit of PV modules is kept 50000. Table 2 depicts the technical and financial aspects of the PV system.

Table 2: PV module details

S.No	Factors	Detail
1	Capital cost	800 \$/kW
2	Replacement	750 \$/kW
3	O&M cost	10 \$/kW/year
4	Derating factor	80%
5	Life time	25 years

DC/AC converter:

To meet the needs of the load, the electricity generated by the PV system is in the form of AC power. To turn DC into AC, a DC/AC power converter is required. Generic system converters are then used. The upper limit of converters is kept 25000. The converter system's various features are listed in Table 3. Table 3 DC/AC converter details

S.No	Features	Detail
1	Capital Cost	200 \$/kW
2	Replacement	200 \$/kW
3	O&M Cost	0 \$/kW/year
4	Relative Capacity	100%
5	Life Time	15 years
6	Efficiency	95%

Wind Turbine:

The generic 3KW model of wind turbine is used in the present work. The upper limit of wind turbines is kept 6000. The various parameters of the system are described in Table 4.

Table 4: Details of wind turbine

S.No	Features	Details
1	Capital Cost	2000 \$/kW
2	Replacement	2000 \$/kW
3	O&M Cost	20 \$/kW/year
4	Hub Height	10m
5	Life Time	15 years

Battery Energy Storage System:

Due to weather conditions, the PV system output fluctuates and varies wildly. It ensures a constant power supply regardless of the weather. In HOMER, battery requirements are calculated in such a way that there is zero unmet demand. The excess energy is stored and then released during nighttime or cloudy periods. Surrate S-260 battery is considered for the backup purpose. The upper limit of batteries is kept 165000. Battery parameter details are shown in Table 5.

Table 5: Battery details

S.No	Features	Details
1	Capital Cost	300 \$/kW
2	Replacement	250 \$/kW
3	O&M Cost	5 \$/kW/year
4	Nominal Voltage	12V
5	Life Time	12 years
6	Ah Capacity	260Ah
7	Kwh Capacity	3.12kWh
8	Roundtrip Efficiency	80%

Grid:

The selected location is well connected with the grid. So, in the simulation grid connectivity is considered. In HOMER, grid is connected with the option of the schedule rates. The electricity supplied by the grid is purchased at a rate of 0.1 US cents per kilowatt hour (kWh) and is sold back to the utility at a rate of 0.05 US cents per kWh. The mean out frequency, mean repair time and repair time variability are 365, 2 hr and 10% respectively.

Results and Discussion:

As stated before, the primary objective of this research is to suggest the optimum hybrid power system capable of providing continuous electricity to inhabitants of the chosen area while also maximizing the contribution of renewable energy sources to the system. For economic and technical study, the suggested configuration of the system is simulated in HOMER software. To find the optimal configuration, each configuration is evaluated based on its COE and NPC to establish its economic and environmental viability.

a). PVWG-OnNM Configuration:

For this configuration, the hybrid system with PV-wind and grid in on-net metering condition is used. The results were compared using net present cost (NPC) and energy costs (COE). The optimized results are

obtained for the 28960 kW PV, 19756 strings of battery, 22448 kW converter and 9,99,999 kW of grid. The COE for this configuration is US\$0.049. Table 6 shows the values of the NPC of the all components. The maximum capital and operating cost is used in solar PV. The battery system has the maximum replacement cost. The solar PV has the maximum total cost.

b). PVWG-OffNM Configuration:

For this configuration, the hybrid system with PV-wind and grid in off-net metering condition is used. The comparison was done on the basis of the net present cost (NPC) and cost of energy (COE). The optimized results are obtained for the 21609 kW PV, 89 units of wind turbine, 20026 strings of battery, 19196 kW converter and 9,99,999 kW of grid. The COE for this configuration is US\$0.077. Table 7 shows the values of the NPC of the all components. The maximum capital cost is used in solar PV while the grid has the maximum operating cost. The battery system has the maximum replacement cost. The grid has the maximum total cost.

c). PVW Configuration:

The hybrid system with PV-wind without is also analyzed. The optimal size of the hybrid system is obtained from the Homer is presented in Table 4.16. The comparison was done on the basis of the net present cost (NPC) and cost of energy (COE). The optimized results are obtained for the 47917 kW PV, 2563 generic 3kW, 165000 strings of battery, and 23698 kW converters. The COE for this configuration is US\$0.253. Table 8 shows the values of the NPC of the all components. The maximum capital, operating and replacement cost is used in solar PV.

Table 6: Net present cost (in US\$) for PVWG-OnNM

S.No	Name	Capital	Operating	Replacement	Salvage	Total
1	Generic flat plate PV	23167745	3743767	0.00	0.00	26911512
2	Grid	0.00	121226	0.00	0.00	121226
3	Surratte S-260	5926800	1276980	3740234	1084578	9859436
4	System converter	4489632	0.00	1904833	3258508	6035957
5	System	33584177	4899521	5645068	1443087	42685680

Table 7: Net present cost (in US\$) PVWG-OffNM

S.No	Name	Capital	Operating	Replacement	Salvage	Total
1	Generic flat plate PV	17287445	2793546	0.00	0.00	20080992
2	Generic 3kW	178000	23010	75520	14213	262317
3	Grid	0.00	22736377	0.00	0.00	22736377
4	Surrette S-260	6007800	1294432	3791351	1099400	9994182
5	System converter	3239292	0.00	1374346	258665	4354973
	System	26712538	26847367	5241218	1372280	57428844

Table 8: Net present cost (in US\$) for PVW

S.No	Name	Capital	Operating	Replacement	Salvage	Total
1	Generic flat plate PV	38333333	6194435	0	0	44527768
2	Generic 3KW	5126000	662664	2174827	409324	7554167
3	Surrette S-260	49500000	10665201	32123617	8411122	83877696
4	System converter	4739583	0	2010881	378468	6371996
	System	97698916	17522300	36309325	9198914	142331628

d). Comparative Analysis of Three Configurations:

Figure 10: Comparison of COE

Figure 10 shows the comparison of the three models on the basis of NPC and COE. The off-grid system (PVW) shows the maximum NPC and COE. So, this configuration is not suitable for the hybrid system. PVWG-OffNM shows the less NPC and COE as compare to the PVW while more than the PVWG-OnNM. The

system with on net metering shows the minimum NPC and COE which makes it most suitable for the hybrid system for the current location and load.

Figure 11: Comparison of NPC

Conclusion:

The study analyses the technical and economic feasibility of a hybrid power system for the hamlet of Bohar in Haryana, India. For load and resource evaluation purposes, data is gathered from the chosen site. HOMER software is used to simulate three distinct configurations of RERs in combination. The findings indicate that the PVWG-OnNM arrangement is the most cost effective, with a COE of \$0.049/kWh, compared to \$0.1/kWh when grid electricity is bought. At all times throughout the year, demand is completely fulfilled. The system's optimal design includes a 28960 KW photovoltaic system, 19756 battery strings, 22448 KW converters, and 9,99,999 KW of grid power.

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